

NATURE OF GENDER OF JURIDICAL RHETORIC IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the nature of gender in contemporary linguistics and rhetorical law. The biological and social differences between men and women are generally referred to as gender. The fact that words in languages can be both masculine and feminine may also be known to people. At first look, it can seem as though linguistic gender naturally mirrors gender in nature.

Keywords: *gender, linguistic phenomena, stereotypical ideas, socio-sexual relations, masculine and feminine, sex, male and female;*

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada zamonaviy tilshunoslik va ritorik huquqda jinsning tabiati muhokama qilinadi. Erkaklar va ayollar o'rtasidagi biologik va ijtimoiy farqlar odatda gender deb ataladi. Tillardagi so'zlarning ham erkak, ham ayol bo'lishi mumkinligi ham odamlarga ma'lum bo'lishi mumkin. Bir qarashda, lingvistik jins tabiatda jinsni aks ettiradigandek tuyulishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: *gender, lingvistik hodisalar, stereotipik g'oyalar, ijtimoiy-jinsiy munosabatlar, erkak va ayol, jins, erkak va ayol;*

АБСТРАКТ

В данной статье рассматривается природа гендера в современной лингвистике и риторическом праве. Биологические и социальные различия между мужчинами и женщинами обычно называют гендерными. То, что слова в языках могут быть как мужского, так и женского рода, тоже может быть известно людям. На первый взгляд может показаться, что языковой пол естественным образом отражает пол в природе.

Ключевые слова: *гендер, языковые явления, стереотипные представления, социально-половые отношения, мужское и женское начало, пол, мужское и женское;*

The study of language phenomena has seen significant anthropocentric progress in recent decades. In such linguistic subjects, gender studies, which are presently generating a great deal of attention in our country, have a particular position. Gender studies' central thesis is that it refers to a certain set of cultural characteristics that have an impact on how men and women interact in society. Studies on gender have concentrated on cultural and social aspects that influence how society perceives men and women, how people act when they identify as one sex or the other, and stereotypical notions about characteristics – everything that moves the gender issue from the domain of biology to the domain of social life and culture.

The system of socio-sexual relations represents the internally contradictory and concurrently dynamic ratio of male and female substrates, gender relations as a sociocultural superstructure over biological truth, and these concepts are all deeply established in culture and language[6, 43]. Data from several sciences must be incorporated into the essay when examining gender from this perspective. Psycholinguistics, ethnolinguistics, cognitive linguistics, intercultural communication, pragmalinguistics, sociolinguistics, and other fields all contribute to the linguistic analysis of gender. In linguistics, gender is viewed as a cognitive

phenomenon that shows itself in the different speech patterns and linguistic cliches of communicators.

The analysis of the expansion of meaning of the concept *gender* in English shows that it is a polysemic term with at least three different meanings in juridical discourse[1, 54]:

- (1) *gender* = *sex* or *woman/women*. In Uzbek – *jins* yoki *ayol/ayollar*
- (2) *gender* as in the biological theory. In Uzbek – *ijtimoiy jins*
- (3) *gender* as in the social theory

Even within a single juridical culture, the same juridical term may express several concepts depending on the context in which it is used. The frequency of polysemy can be explained by the fact that juridical systems are in a constant state of change, and they also influence each other. Therefore, even from the juridical point of view, polysemic juridical terms make difficulties for the interpretation of juridical norms. There are at least three ways how the legislator can avoid or solve the problem of polysemy:

1) The legislature defines the polysemic term in a normative legal document, giving it just one interpretation. This technique can make the term's meaning more or less obvious and unambiguous [5, 78]. A legal word is allegedly supposed to have the same meaning each and every time it is used once it has been defined [3, 45];

2) the legislator respects only one style of juridical writing, that is, he uses the term only in one precise sense throughout the juridical act [2, 21]. In this situation, a juridical definition of the term is not necessary. Butt and Castle point out that a definition of the term is unnecessary 'if the meaning of the word or phrase is clear or can be readily ascertained from the context' [1, 23];

3) the legislator uses a neologism, that is, invents a new juridical term/word. It can be a completely new one (for example, it could be a new word *jins* in Uzbek), or it can also be created as a composed word, for example, it could be *ijtimoiy jinsiy aloqa*, *ijtimoiy oila* in Uzbek.

The necessity to thoroughly examine how gender studies in linguistics have developed as a new field of Uzbek humanitarian knowledge determines the significance of this study. The purpose of this paper is to evaluate language gender studies in our country. Scientific articles have paid particular attention to the history of the creation and evolution of gender linguistics, the distinction between the concepts of "gender" and "sex," the definitional possibilities for gender, and the practicality of using gender as a text-formation parameter.

By assessing the areas of gender mainstreaming, we found that the three widely accepted methods to gender studies had a big impact on the development of Uzbek linguistics. The first method's objective is to identify linguistic variations that could be explained by characteristics of the redistribution of social power in society. This strategy is restricted to the interpretation of solely social aspects of language used by men and women. The term "masculine" or "feminine" language refers to a functional derivative of the primary language used in situations where speaking partners are at different social levels. According to science [6, 33], "Feminine" and "Masculine" language may be boiled down to linguistic quirks that the socio-psycholinguistic method has identified. Researchers in this discipline must consider statistical indicators or average parameter definitions because they offer a foundation for creating psycholinguistic hypotheses about the distinctions between male and female speech behavior. The proponents of the third option frequently emphasize the cognitive aspect of gender differences in language behavior. They find that, in addition to determining the frequency of differences and using its indicators, it is more crucial to develop thorough linguistic models of the cognitive foundations of language categories. It is also important to note that all three techniques are seen as complimentary in the current scientific paradigm and that their joint use is necessary for explanatory power to exist. It's also important to keep in mind that the researchers' major areas of interest ended up being the speaker's personality and

speech behavior. Female and male audiences, respectively, present the speaker and the text with the "speaker's macro factor" and "text macro factor" [3, 21] criteria.

Several interpretations of gender's essence in arguments in support of bio- and socio-deterministic methods have led to a variety of methodological orientations in modern domestic science. Research into the mechanisms and characteristics of how the author's gender identity manifests itself in texts, as well as discussion of gender differences, which are the focus of numerous recent linguistic studies, can both be built upon the theoretical material examined for the preparation of this article.

THE LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. Cameron, D. (2005) Language, gender and sexuality: current issues and new directions. *Applied Linguistics*, 26: 482–
2. Charlesworth, H. (2005) Not waving but drowning: gender mainstreaming and human rights in the United Nations. *Harvard Human Rights Journal*, 18: 1–18.
3. Charlesworth, H. (2013) Le sexe de l'Etat en droit international. In S. HenetteVauchez (prés.) *Sexe, genre et droit international*. Paris: Pedone.
4. Charruau, J. (2015) L'introduction de la notion de genre en droit français. *Revue française de droit administrative, RFDA*, No 1, Janvier-Février: 127–136.
5. Cook, G. (2003) *Applied Linguistics*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
6. Cook, G. (2011) British applied linguistics: impacts of and impacts on. In *The Impact of Applied Linguistics. Proceedings of the 44th Annual Meeting of the British Association for Applied Linguistics* (pp. 35–58). University of the West of England.